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POSSIBLE APPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

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ABSTRACT

The increasing social relevance of artificial intelligence (AI) requires a differentiated examination of its potential and challenges, especially in the context of public administration. This thesis examines the possible applications of weak AI in structures and analyzes its contribution to the digital transformation of government services. Key fields of application, such as administration, infrastructure, security and environmental and climate protection, are identified and evaluated in terms of their technical and social implications. The focus is on the question of how AI systems can contribute to increasing efficiency and automating processes. The benefits of AI-supported systems in the public sector are clarified. At the same time, structural deficits such as a lack of interoperability, limited data availability and a lack of acceptance will be addressed. Particular attention is paid to ethical and ecological aspects. The use of AI is not only associated with efficiency gains, but also with significant environmental impacts and potential power shifts within the administration. This ambivalence underlines the need for transparent, legally compliant and socially accepted AI applications. The work concludes with the realization that AI in public administration offers a high potential for innovation, but requires responsible and interdisciplinary implementation. In-depth research into the long-term effects is essential if the technology is to be used sustainably and in the public interest.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, weak AI, strong AI, public administration.

INTRODUCTION

Society's focus on AI has increased in recent years, with the critical examination of this topic playing a decisive role in its further use and equally influencing its acceptance (cf. Bory et al. 2024). There are areas of application in which the use of AI can bring benefits for society. One example is the use of the Chat Generative Pretraining Transformer (ChatGPT) as a tool to improve documentation procedures and documentation quality, which can improve treatment success through greater treatment precision (cf. Gosak 2024). For this reason, an examination of the topic of AI in the context of the ongoing digital transformation of the state is relevant for social coexistence as a whole (cf. Klenk et al. 2025). This article examines the extent to which the use of weak AI in public administration can contribute to increasing efficiency without jeopardizing data protection standards and social aspects.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The term AI is used in a variety of disciplines and contexts, which is why there is currently no standardized definition. To make it easier to understand, the following is a terminological clarification of key terms. In current discourse, AI is primarily understood as the ability to communicate and reason in a human-like manner. The term is often equated with machine

learning (cf. Stanford University 2025). This refers to statistical processes that recognize and interpret patterns in data (cf. Visio AI 2025). In the specialist literature, a distinction is also made between *weak* and *strong* AI (cf. Eschker & Liu 2024)

Current systems are classified as weak AI as they are limited to specific areas of application. Nevertheless, they are becoming increasingly important, both in an industrial context and in everyday life, for example through the use of chatbots (cf. Bory et al. 2024). The focus of research is on explainable multimodal AI, which processes complex, sometimes incomprehensible data sources. While early AI systems such as decision trees or the Bayesian model were comprehensible, today's data volume makes transparency more difficult. Generative models enable new, logically interpretable outputs, but also make weaknesses such as hallucinations visible (cf. Eschker & Liu 2024). So far, strong AI only exists hypothetically and describes systems that could surpass humans in terms of cognitive abilities. The European Parliament referred to this form as the "fifth element" - associated with ideas of consciousness and understanding. Due to a lack of practical realization, however, its definition remains open (cf. Mindsquare 2025).

The aim of this article is to analyze the application potential of weak AI in public administration, both in citizen-oriented and internal administrative processes. Employee survey topic areas such as infrastructure, security, environment and ethics are considered separately. Digitalization in public administration is not only a technical process, but also a political and social process that is influenced by democratic participation (cf. Klenk et al. 2025). The first digital wave enabled global networking. New technologies such as social media and big data have led to an exponential increase in data, the processing of which must be increasingly automated (cf. Elamrani 2025).

Administration is divided into a citizen-oriented and an internal dimension (cf. Haufe 2025). Regardless of the field of application, the implementation of suitable AI processes requires technological feasibility and qualified specialist staff. Some major cities are already demonstrating the use of AI in the digitalization of administrative services, such as the semi-automated issuing of resident parking permits (cf. Klenk et al. 2025). Chatbots improve accessibility, while service robots provide linguistic and functional support for citizens' concerns. In the long term, personalized, emotionally adaptive advisory systems will emerge. Standardized identification systems are still lacking, which creates media disruptions. The Online Access Act of 2027 was intended to counteract this, but was unable to achieve the goal of complete digitalization by 2022 (cf. Röbbcke & Düser 2025)

According to forecasts, there will be a shortage of over one million skilled workers in public administrations by 2030. In order to effectively counter this structural deficit, the comprehensive digitalization and automation of administrative processes is of central importance. Empirical studies show that up to 64% of the hours worked in public administrations can in principle be automated (. This considerable rationalization potential can be tapped into through the targeted use of automation technologies and AI (cf. Mach 2025). By relieving employees of repetitive routine activities, resources can be freed up for more complex, non-standardizable tasks. At the same time, sources of error can be reduced and organizational performance can be maintained, even under conditions of increasing staff shortages. Automation therefore represents not only a technical, but also a strategic response to the demographic and structural challenges facing public administration (cf. World Economic Forum 2025).

In the future, AI systems could use social media to identify aggregated citizens' wishes and incorporate them into political decision-making processes, for example when adjusting opening hours or fees. Targeted evaluations of social benefits such as the child building allowance would also be possible (cf. Klenk et al. 2025). The ongoing staff shortage in statistical administration is reflected in the forecast tripling of case numbers (cf. Funke 2024). AI-supported systems could make processes more efficient here, for example in application procedures or clerking (cf. Elamrani 2025). City administrations are increasingly investing in networked systems and IT expertise, but are faced with unanswered questions regarding data protection and the legal structure (cf. Klenk et al. 2025). AI is being used in a variety of ways, and the figure below illustrates the opportunities and challenges that arise from AI implementations:

Figure1 : Navigating the complex impact of AI
Source: Own presentation

- **Infrastructure:** AI-based systems analyze road conditions, traffic density and maintenance cycles. The aim is resource-conserving, safety-oriented infrastructure development (cf. Köhnecke 2023). In the education sector, AI- applications could support didactic design. Individualized professional development through intelligent search systems also appears realistic (cf. Funke 2024).
- **Security:** AI systems are used in tax proceedings and by the police to analyze risks and predict criminal offenses (cf. AlgorithmWatch 2024). The EU's planned *AI Act* is intended to regulate potentially discriminatory applications (cf. Mehner et al. 2023). Dynamic AI forecasts are being tested for natural hazards such as strum. The aim is to alert and protect critical infrastructure in good time (cf. Burrichter et al. 2025).
- **Health:** Digital patient records enable faster data access for medical staff and research. Broad acceptance among the population contrasts with mistrust of state institutions (cf. Haug et al. 2024).

- **Environmental and climate protection:** AI can achieve significant CO₂ savings through optimized resource planning in agriculture and construction (cf. Zhang et al. 2023). At the same time, training large models causes considerable emissions and energy consumption (cf. Farmonaut 2024).
- **Ethical reflection:** The ecological balance of AI projects is ambivalent. In addition to CO₂ emissions, experts criticize the lack of transparency in data usage. Political decisions on environmental measures must therefore be made by humans (cf. Wang et al. 2024). Surveillance technologies harbor the risk of violating civil liberties. Algorithmic discrimination can also reinforce social inequalities (cf. Klenk et al. 2025).

In addition, human-like AI agents influence social interaction by dehumanizing real people and reinforcing stereotypical perceptions (cf. Kim & McGill 2024). Initial studies show that modern AI systems already pass the Turing test (cf. Jones et al. 2025).

METHODOLOGY

This article is based exclusively on the method of document analysis for data collection within the framework of qualitative research. With regard to the topic under investigation, relevant specialist literature, scientific studies and relevant publications are systematically selected and analyzed in order to enable a well-founded and differentiated examination of the topic. The article begins with a terminological clarification of key terms. Building on this, the topic is contextualized and discussed using the analyzed sources. The work concludes with a critical reflection on the results and an outlook on future fields of research and application.

RESULTS

This article focuses exclusively on the potential applications of AI, the development of which was initially accompanied by unspecific objectives, as a sound technological understanding was not yet available (cf. Mindsquare 2025). The introduction of such systems is embedded in a complex adaptation process that promotes the social acceptance of machine-based substitution of repetitive human activities. Despite initial hurdles, numerous fields of application already exist, particularly in the area of citizen-oriented services. A central goal of AI initiatives is to actively involve citizens in administrative processes, even if they have no prior technical knowledge. This transfer is to be made possible by AI-supported systems (cf. Tzortzis 2024).

The development and integration of AI-supported solutions in public authorities is a central concern of current research projects (cf. Klenk et al. 2025). Various relevant concepts for the use of AI exist in the education sector. However, their implementation requires both the expansion of digital infrastructures and an institutionalized interface between technical systems and pedagogical actors. There is also the question of long-term financial viability (cf. Schleiss et al. 2023). AI has already been used successfully for several years to prevent and investigate crime in the security sector. However, new European legal requirements are increasingly restricting this practice, meaning that the systems must be adapted both technically and legally to changing framework conditions (cf. Mehner et al. 2023).

With regard to the ecological impact of AI, it is noticeable that empirically robust studies for rural areas are still largely lacking. While urban areas benefit from advanced infrastructure and higher efficiency potential, there are high implementation hurdles, especially in a rural context. In addition, the ecological footprint of many AI systems has so far been insufficiently

documented, which indicates a considerable lack of transparency with regard to the actual environmental costs (cf. Bian et al. 2023). Transparency is a fundamental prerequisite for the responsible use of AI, both for the traceability of decision-making processes and to avoid systematic distortions.

Increasing digitalization in the public sector harbours structural risks. In particular, a possible centralization of data sovereignty can lead to a shift in power and impair the ability of decentralized administrative units to act (cf. Klenk et al. 2025). Last but not least, the use of AI raises social questions regarding interpersonal behavior. Initial empirical evidence points to potentially negative effects on social interactions and human perception, which require critical ethical reflection (cf. Köhnecke et al. 2023).

The question "To what extent can the use of weak artificial intelligence in public administration contribute to increasing efficiency without jeopardizing democratic principles, data protection standards and social participation?" can therefore be answered as follows. The use of weak AI in public administration offers significant potential for increasing efficiency, particularly through the automation of repetitive processes, intelligent data processing and citizen-oriented interaction systems such as chatbots or service robots (cf. Klenk et al. 2025). Examples such as the automated issuing of resident parking permits in Frankfurt or AI-supported application processes show that technological support can relieve the burden on human resources and shorten response times. Particularly in the context of the increasing staff shortage, the use of AI is a means of maintaining administrative capacity to act (cf. Henger & Engler 2022).

At the same time, however, compliance with basic democratic principles is essential. These include transparency, traceability and the guarantee of participation. Critical voices emphasize that the increased use of AI systems could lead to a centralization of data sovereignty and thus jeopardize the autonomy of decentralized administrative units (cf. Klenk et al. 2025). Data protection issues remain unresolved, particularly with regard to the processing of personal information and the integration of social media for decision-making processes.

AI systems must be designed in such a way that all population groups, regardless of technical competence or social background, have equal access to digital administrative services. Without accessible systems, there is a risk that already disadvantaged groups will be further marginalized. Studies also point to the risks that AI can dehumanize social interactions and reinforce stereotypical perceptions (cf. Kim & McGill 2024). The contribution of weak AI to increasing efficiency in public administration is significant, but only sustainable if its implementation is accompanied by clear ethical guidelines, comprehensive data protection regulation and socially inclusive design principles. Responsible, participatory use is therefore essential.

DISCUSSION

The results presented here show that AI offers significant innovation potential for public administration, be it in the automation of processes, the optimization of infrastructure or improved data processing in the health and security sector. It is clear that AI as a tool is not good or bad per se, but that its benefits depend largely on the framework conditions, the implementation strategy and ethical reflection. On the positive side, the possibility of using AI-based technologies to make administrative processes more efficient, partially compensate for staff shortages and improve citizen-oriented services should be emphasized. Especially in the context of increasing demands for service quality and transparency, AI can help to compensate

for existing deficits. AI also opens up new avenues for resource-conserving planning and timely crisis intervention in environmental and transport policy.

At the same time, these potentials must be weighed up critically. The lack of technical infrastructure, lack of interoperability and the high energy consumption of large AI models pose significant challenges. In addition, the transparency of many AI systems is still inadequate. This is particularly problematic in security-relevant areas where algorithmic predictions can have a direct impact on human lives. While large sections of the population could benefit from a higher quality of service, others are sceptical about the technology, whether due to concerns about surveillance or the *dehumanization* of public interaction. These fears are reinforced by the discussion about human-like AI agents that could change social relationships and reinforce stereotypical perceptions.

The ethical discourse, which has so far been insufficiently conducted institutionally, is particularly critical. Although the first normative guidelines exist with the planned EU AI Act, their implementation remains a political and legal challenge. AI must not become a substitute for political decision-makers, especially when it comes to environmental or safety issues. Responsibility must ultimately remain with humans, even if AI is used in an advisory and supportive capacity.

The successful and responsible use of AI in public administration requires not only technological innovation, but above all an integrative approach that takes equal account of legal, ethical and social aspects. Only under these conditions can AI develop its potential as a contribution to public services of general interest without jeopardizing fundamental democratic values.

CONCLUSIONS

Despite the often-cited efficiency gains promised by weak AI in public administration, the current discourse remains disturbingly technocentric and largely blind to its far-reaching normative and social consequences (cf. Bian et al. 2023). The dominant narrative, driven by a euphoric belief in optimization, automation, and resource efficiency, systematically downplays or outright ignores critical risks, among them a lack of transparency, growing social inequalities, deepening technological dependencies, and the environmental costs of AI systems.

Particularly troubling is the institutional failure to establish robust ethical oversight structures. The near-total absence of mechanisms for democratic control and critical reflection on the boundaries of technical delegation represents a serious erosion of public accountability. The automation of public services is not a neutral process. It inherently reshapes power dynamics, redistributes access, and alters the relationship between citizens and the state.

Efficiency gains in areas like citizen services, infrastructure, or HR management may be technically impressive, but they come at the price of unresolved political tensions. Without transparent documentation of ecological impacts, inclusive participation of marginalized communities, and safeguards against algorithmic bias. AI in the public sector risks becoming a vehicle for technocratic governance that displaces democratic deliberation. Treating AI merely as a tool for administrative modernization is not only short-sighted, it is politically negligent. AI must be understood and regulated as a deeply political field that demands critical engagement, not uncritical implementation.

The analysis clearly reveals that the use of artificial intelligence in the public sector poses significant risks to democratic principles, social justice, and ecological sustainability if not accompanied by robust and enforceable oversight mechanisms. According to Klenk et al. (2025) independent, interdisciplinary AI ethics councils must be established at the municipal level, not as mere advisory bodies, but with binding veto powers to prevent the deployment of systems that endanger fundamental rights or exacerbate societal power imbalances.

Moreover, it is unacceptable for AI systems to be introduced without prior environmental and social impact assessments. A systematic evaluation of their effects on the climate, inclusion, and social equity must become mandatory. The results of these assessments must be made publicly accessible, anything less undermines transparency and accountability (cf. Kim & McGill 2024). The ongoing neglect of public AI literacy is equally problematic. A democratic society cannot afford a deepening digital divide. The state has a responsibility not only to invest in education but also to develop participatory formats that enable meaningful public involvement in the design and oversight of AI systems.

Particularly alarming is the current lack of transparency in public AI deployments. Without legally mandated disclosure requirements, concerning training data, decision-making processes, and error margins, democratic control is virtually impossible. A publicly accessible and independently audited AI register is therefore not optional but essential to break through opaque power structures and prevent the misuse of algorithmic systems in the public domain.

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